

TABLE 1 - PLASTIC VISCOSITY AND YIELD VALUE OF 10% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION DURING INTERACTION WITH DIFFERENT POLYELECTROLYTES

Polyelectrolyte added	Parameter*	Volume of 10% solution added to 100 ml 10% Na-bentonite suspension (ml)				
		2	5	10	20	30
Na-silicate	A	17.8	16.84	20.62	27.17	36.67
	B	0	0	0	0	0.034 12
Na-hexametaphosphate	A	15.63	16.54	17.74	18.04	20.74
	B	0	0	0	0	0
Na-polyacrylate	A	14.31	15.73	18.42	20.32	24.92
	B	0	0	0	0	0.034 12
Na-amylose phosphate	A	16.84	16.54	17.03	18.04	17.88
	B	0	0	0	0	0.010 23
Na-lauryl sulphate	A	27.67	30.52	27.54	20.14	14.68
	B	0.617 7	0.655 2	0.515 3	0.484 6	0.143 3
Polyvinyl alcohol	A	23.09	26.46	25.25	20.65	14.21
	B	0.409 6	0.614 4	0.505 2	0.320 7	0
Gelatin	A	18.66	18.64	19.48	22.84	23.15
	B	0.129 3	0.211 5	0.430 0	0.532 3	0.430 0
Na-carboxymethyl cellulose	A	125.2	171.8	322.1	365.1	529.1
	B	3.924	1.536	3.242	4.266	9.725

*A = Plastic viscosity ($\times 10^3$ poise), B = yield value (dyne cm^{-2}).

progressive addition but in a stepwise manner and the change was not so significant.

Disappearance of yield value was observed with inorganic polyions—Na-polyacrylate and Na-amylose phosphate which is solely related to the mode of particle association and to the stability of the complex at the edge of the clay crystal. Amongst the polyions, Na-carboxymethylcellulose exhibited significantly high yield value which might be associated with the high degree of polymerisation of the reagent. The yield value in this case initially decreased followed by sharp rise on further addition. Some relationship with respect to yield value change was noticed with gelatin only upto 20 ml addition.

Thus it is noted that the stability of the 10% bentonite suspension on progressive addition of polyelectrolyte, which contains functional group distributed along the entire length of the chain, improved with silicate, hexametaphosphate, polyacrylate and amylose phosphate. In other cases, mode of particle association was such that it led to change of flow behaviour to non-Newtonian direction.

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Heat of Transport of Water in Soil Fractions, Model Soils and an Alluvial Soil

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SOME reports of studies on thermal diffusion of water in soil have appeared¹. Recently, Sanyal *et al.*²⁻⁴ have examined the phenomena of thermal diffusion in soil/clay systems. The present paper reports such thermally induced migrations in soil components isolated from an alluvial soil in order to examine the specific effects and then extend these experiments to 'model soil' composed thereof. The paper also reports the non-isothermal diffusion of water across the given alluvial soil for providing a comparison to results obtained with the synthetic soils.

Experimental

The soil used was an alluvial surface soil (0-15 cm) collected from Baruipur, 24-Parganas, West

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF MODEL SOILS

Soil	Percent content by weight of				Soil texture
	Sand	Silt	Clay	Humic acid	
MS ₁	25	30	35	—	Sandy clay loam
MS ₂	23	50	27	—	Silty loam
MS ₃	20	40	40	—	Silty clay
MS ₄	35	29	35	1	Sandy clay loam

TABLE 2—SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ALLUVIAL SOIL FRACTIONS, MODEL SOILS AND ALLUVIAL SOIL

Sample	Maximum water holding capacity %	Cation exchange capacity meq/100 g	Specific surface area m ² g ⁻¹
Sand	38.0	2.5	9.6
Silt	46.0	3.7	32.4
Clay	69.0	36.2	263.3
MS ₁	55.0	10.2	68.5
MS ₂	51.0	13.7	71.8
MS ₃	65.0	18.7	85.0
MS ₄	57.0	21.2	91.2
Alluvial soil ^a	59.0	22.5	104.9

^aSome important physicochemical properties: pH = 7.3, organic matter = 1.3%, CEC = 22.5 meq/100 g, texture = sandy loam; clay = 31%, water holding capacity = 57% moisture (by weight).

Results and Discussion

The important physicochemical properties and heat of transport of water ($\hat{Q}_w$) in the soil separates, the given model soils and the alluvial soil are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Positive values of heat of transport of water ($\hat{Q}_w$) correspond to an absorption of heat behind the diffusing entity and a liberation ahead in course of diffusional migration through the central chamber. A plausible explanation may be sought in terms of the structural order present in bulk water in the central chamber.

The $\hat{Q}_w$ value is also seen to fall from that for sand through silt to clay (Table 3). This may possibly be attributed to concomitant smaller particle size, leading to progressively higher surface area which would narrow down the 'entropy gain' of water entrapped inside the porous material. The latter causes a lowering of $\hat{Q}_w$. That the $\hat{Q}_w$ values bear an inverse relationship with the specific surface area, and the C.E.C. of the soil separates (Tables 2 and 3) also corroborates the above picture. In agreement with such a trend, a gradual fall in $\hat{Q}_w$ from MS₁ to MS₄ among the model soils studied is also observed as the corresponding texture becomes finer and the specific surface area increases (Tables 2 and 3). The given alluvial soil exhibiting a $\hat{Q}_w$ value, which fits in with the present

TABLE 3—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER IN SOIL SEPARATES, MODEL SOILS AND THE ALLUVIAL SOIL

Sample	Moisture content %	Mean temp. (T _m) °C	(-ΔP/ΔT) _{s,t} × 10 ³ atm/deg	V _w ml mol ⁻¹	$\hat{Q}_w^0$ J mol ⁻¹
Sand	38.0	35.5	3.13	18.05	1.76 (±0.086)
Silt	46.0	35.5	2.40	18.06	1.36 (±0.062)
Clay	69.0	35.1	1.69	18.04	0.95 (±0.045)
MS ₁	55.0	35.6	2.75	18.05	1.55 (±0.054)
MS ₂	51.0	35.1	2.48	18.04	1.39 (±0.043)
MS ₃	65.0	35.3	2.35	18.04	1.32 (±0.036)
MS ₄	57.0	35.1	2.34	18.09	1.33 (±0.034)
Alluvial soil	59.0	35.6	2.21	18.10	1.24 (±0.017)

The Bengal. The soil fractions were isolated from the soil by following the standard sedimentations techniques. Model soils⁵ were then prepared by admixing H-form of soil components in definite proportions (Table 1). The non-isothermal diffusion cell used was based on a design of Sanyal and Bandyopadhyay⁶. The heat of transport of water was obtained by having recourse to the relation,

$$\hat{Q}_w = -V_w T_m (\Delta P / \Delta T)_{s,t} \quad (1)$$

where $(\Delta P / \Delta T)_{s,t}$ refers to the steady state value across the sandwiched soil chamber, while T_m and V_w are the mean (absolute) temperature and molar volume of water, respectively.

trend, noted for the model soils prepared, also suggests that the thermal diffusion effect, as demonstrated in soils, is essentially additive in nature, depending primarily on the specific contributions of various soil fractions present.

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Reactions of Ethyl α -Naphthylpropiolate with Phenylacetamide, Benzyl Cyanide, Ethyl Phenylacetate and 1-Acetylinole

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THE condensation between arylacetamide¹⁻⁴, benzyl cyanides^{5,6}, ethyl acetate^{6,7} and *N*-acetylinole⁸ with ethyl phenylpropiolate has been reported earlier. The results of the analogous condensation of the above nucleophiles with ethyl α -naphthylpropiolate are reported here.

The reaction of arylacetamide with ethyl α -naphthylpropiolate in boiling benzene in presence of powdered sodium afforded 1 (Table I). The reaction proceeded either by Claisen ester condensation of the amide anion or Michael addition of the carbanion generated from ArCH₂CONH₂ to the acetylenic ester followed by cyclisation. The Claisen route seems more likely by analogy to the condensation of benzyl cyanide⁵⁻⁵ or ethyl phenylacetate^{6,7} with acetylenic ester. The condensation of ethyl α -naphthylpropiolate with benzyl cyanide and ethyl phenylacetate gave 2 and 3, respectively, as the main products, evidently arising by Claisen ester condensation of the reactants. Ir and pmr spectra (Table I) indicate that these two products exist predominatly, if not exclusively, in the enolic form.

via a Claisen addition of the carbanion of the 1-acetylinole to the ester function of the propiolate. It should be mentioned here that the reaction of phenylpropionic ester with 1-acetylinole yielded two products, 5-aryl-1-(indol-1-yl)-pent-4-yn-1,3-diones and ethyl β -(indol-1-yl)cinnamates as a result of Claisen and Michael reactions, respectively⁸. Compound 4 gave positive ferric chloride test, but attempt to convert it into the corresponding 4-pyrones was unsuccessful.

1; X = H, *p*-Cl and *m*-F

2; R = CN

3; R = CO₂Et

1-4; Ar = α -Naphthyl

Experimental

Ir spectra were measured with a Unicam SP-200 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra with a Varian A-60 D spectrometer for solutions in deuteriochloroform containing TMS as the internal standard. The compounds were analysed at the Max Planck Institute, Ruhr, West Germany. Melting points were determined on a Kofler hot stage and are uncorrected. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE PYRIDIN-2,6-DIONES (1)

Substituent x	Yield %	M.p. °C	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		δ (CDCl ₃)			
			NH	CO	NH (br, s, exchangeable)	3-H (d, J, 2Hz)	ArH (m)	5-H (d, J, 2Hz)
H	41	178	3 400	1 750, 1 710	11.90	8.30	7.50	5.20
<i>p</i> -Cl	40	182	3 410	1 745, 1 715	11.95	8.25	7.40	5.18
<i>m</i> -F	47	220	3 390	1 740, 1 710	11.85	8.20	7.55	5.30

The condensation of ethyl α -naphthylpropiolate with 1-acetylinole in the presence of sodium ethoxide at 0° yielded the β -ketoamide (4) as the only product. Here also the reaction proceeds

Ethyl α -naphthylpropiolate: It was prepared from α -formylnaphthalene by the same procedure as described for ethyl phenylpropiolate from benzaldehyde⁹. 3- α -Naphthylacrylic acid, prepared by